

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

SBRT pancreas

Luka Bajčetić

University Clinical Centre of Serbia

Introduction: In order to deliver a better and better dose to the region of interest, the SBRT method of pancreatic irradiation was introduced.

Goal: Precise delivery of a high dose to a small volume with a small number of fractions. The role of the radiotherapy technician during each segment of the entire process, as well as all the specifics of the preparation and performance of pancreatic SBRT therapy.

Methodology: Application of modern irradiation methods with adequate immobilization when using respiratory gating.

Result: The quality and length of survival after applying this method is significantly increased.

Conclusion: If it is known that radiotherapy has the task of irradiating the tumor with a dose that will reduce it or completely destroy it, while at the same time healthy tissues and organs should be spared as much as possible, then this technique is the right choice for irradiating patients with pancreatic cancer. This technique enables us to administer high doses in one session, and the number of fractions is also significantly reduced. As a result, early and late complications are minimized or completely absent.

Key words: SBRT, Respiratory gating, immobilization, high doses of radiation

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2022**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

CIP – Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Mатице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (2022 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress,
November, 05-06 2022 Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula,
Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. - Novi Sad : Institut za
Onkologiju Vojvodine, 2022 (Novi Sad : NS digiprint).
– 56 str. : ilustr. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200.

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 78911241